

THE PLACE OF DEFINITE ARTICLE IN ENGLISH GRAMMAR

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Safarmurodova Maftuna

Termiz State University 3rd course student

Annotation: *This article presents different rules and examples to explain the placement and importance of the definite article “THE” in English grammar.*

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There are 2 types of articles in English. Definite article and indefinite article. In English, there is only one definite article: the. There are 2 indefinite article: a, an. The definite article (the) is used before a noun to indicate that the identity of the noun is known to the reader. The indefinite articles (a, an) are used before a noun that is general or when its identity is not known. There are certain situations in which a noun takes no article. An indefinite article is an article that refers to a noun without specifying it or refers to a noun to introduce it for the first time. For example, the sentence I saw a dog at the park uses the indefinite article a.

The place of the definite article in English grammar is very important. Because some words have different meanings through the placement of a definite article.

For example,

Go to university - (as a student)

Go to the university (not as a student)

Go to school (as a pupil)

Go to the school -go to the school building(not as a pupil)

Go to Church(the purpose is pray)

Go to the Church(just go to the building, the purpose is not praying)

Go to hospital- (as an ill)

Go to the hospital- (just go to the building)

Go to prison- as a prisoner

Go to the prison- just going to the building, not as a prisoner

Go to bed - to lie down

Go to the bed- Go to near the bed

Masalan,

Go to university - õqishga bormoq (talaba sifatida)

Go to the university -universitet binosiga bormoq (boshqa maqsadda)

Go to school -maktabga bormoq (õquvchi sifatida)

Go to the school -maktab binosiga bormoq (boshqa maqsadda)

Go to Church -cherkovga bormoq (siğinish ma'nosida)

Go to the Church -cherkovga bormoq (binosiga bormoq, sig'inish maqsadida emas)

Go to hospital -kasalxonaga bormoq (kasal sifatida)

Go to the hospital -kasalxona binosiga bormoq (boshqa maqsadda)

Go to prison -qamalmoq (maxbus sifatida)

Go to the prison -qamoqxonaga binosiga bormoq (boshqa maqsadda)

Go to bed -yotoqqa bormoq , yotmoq

Go to the bed -kravatni oldiga bormoq

Also in English grammar some words are always preceded by the definite article "the". The definite article that is used before singular and non-singular nouns in the singular and plural derived from the same show pronoun. The definite article is used to distinguish a person or thing from that type of person or thing, and it means the same thing.

* If the noun has an identifier that distinguishes it from a person or object of this type, it is used with a definite article:

The drawer of my writing table is locked.

* The name, which is known from the situation or the content of the text, is used with a definite article:

Please, close the window.

Where is the key ?

*The definite article "the" is used when a previously spoken noun is repeated in a sentence:

When I went out, I saw a flower. The flower was beautiful.

*Used in front of a person or item that is unique in the world or situation:

The sun is shining.

The earth goes round the sun.

*A noun that comes after superlative degree is used with a definite article.

The highest mountains are in Asia.

This is the most interesting book that I have ever read.

*The ordinal numbers are preceded by the definite article "the".

The office is on the second floor.

He is the fourth student that I saw today.

*Country and city names do not receive "The". But before them, when the words "United, States, Emirates, Kingdom" come, before these "the" definite article comes.

For example, The United Kingdom

THE USA- The United States Kingdom.

*But some states and city names always come with the definite article "the".

For example:

The Ukrain.

The Caucasas

The Crimea.

The Transvaal

The Congo

The Netherlands

The Ruhr

The Lebanon

The Philippines

The Hague

The Sudan

The Riviera

The Argentine

As you see, there are a lot of rules of the placement of “the” definite article in English grammar. Learners should always pay attention to these rules.

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